

Geographical origin (home institution) of NESCent visitors years 1-4 (through August 2008). Data consists of unique visits (multiple visits by a single individual are counted only once), and only includes NESCent funded activities (and not hosted meetings).

Years 1-4 United States Map

of Visits by Funded Participants
Based on State of Home Institute

State	Total	State	Total	State	Total
Alabama	2	Louisiana	9	Oklahoma	2
Alaska	2	Maine	2	Oregon	8
Arizona	20	Maryland	21	Pennsylvania	18
California	105	Massachusetts	37	Puerto Rico	4
Colorado	12	Michigan	19	Rhode Island	1
Connecticut	21	Minnesota	9	South Carolina	3
Washington DC	23	Missouri	13	South Dakota	3
Florida	20	Montana	5	Tennessee	5
Georgia	18	Nebraska	3	Texas	13
Hawaii	8	Nevada	2	Utah	9
Idaho	2	New Hampshire	4	Vermont	2
Illinois	25	New Jersey	8	Virginia	19
Indiana	11	New Mexico	7	Washington	15
Iowa	6	New York	50	Wisconsin	8
Kansas	8	North Carolina	266	Wyoming	1
Kentucky	3	Ohio	12	Total	864

Note: Numbers are unique visitors. Data only include visitors from NESCent funded activities and does not include hosted meetings.

Years 1 - 4 World Map # of Unique Visits by Funded Participants

Range	No. of Countries	Percentage
1 to 4	21	65.6%
5 to 10	7	21.9%
11 to 25	1	3.1%
26 to 720	3	9.4%

Years 1-4 World Map

of Visits by Funded Participants
Based on Country of Home Institute

Country	Total	Country	Total	Country	Total
Argentina	4	France	8	New Zealand	3
Australia	8	Germany	18	Norway	1
Bangladesh	1	Hungary	1	Panama	2
Belgium	1	India	1	Portugal	1
Brazil	4	Ireland	1	Singapore	1
Canada	37	Italy	2	Spain	1
Chile	8	Jamaica	1	Sweden	5
Colombia	3	Japan	6	Switzerland	7
Denmark	7	Madagascar	1	United Kingdom	44
Dominican Republic	2	Mexico	1	United States	864
Finland	1	Netherlands	2	<i>Non-US</i>	<i>183</i>
				Total	1047

Note: Numbers are unique visitors. Data only include visitors from NESCent funded activities and does not include hosted meetings.